

PREDICTED STIFFNESS LOSS DUE TO DELAMINATION IN
FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

Three dimensional finite element analysis is used in conducting several case studies on the effect of delamination on the structural properties of various two-ply composite cylinders loaded in axial tension. In all cases, the effect of the damage is quantified through a reduction in axial stiffness of the cylinder. Two different crack geometries (circumferential and axial) and several different layups are considered. The results presented include stiffness, compliance, and energy release rate (ERR) as functions of crack length.

KEYWORDS: Three-Dimensional; Finite Element Analysis; Filament Wound; Stiffness Loss; Delamination; Energy Release Rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

An increasing number of applications involving filament wound composite cylinders has resulted in the need to better understand the effects of localized damage in these structures. Two forms of localized damage which have received attention by the research community are those associated with impact, and those associated with various types of processing induced in situ cracks. To date, most of the research addressing localized damage in filament wound composite cylinders has been empirical in nature and has focused on the effect of impact damage as measured by residual strength. Christofrou and Swanson (1) have presented a model for predicting loss of strength in filament wound composite cylinders subjected to low velocity impact. Their model is based on

a quasi-static analysis of the response of the cylinder using a Fourier series cylindrical shell analysis followed by an application of fracture mechanics to predict strength loss. Yener and Wolcott (2) have developed a three dimensional finite element code for damage assessment of composite cylinders subjected to impact. Their program is capable of handling material nonlinearities as well as nonlinear dynamic transient response. They have used their program to assess damage accumulation in composite pressure vessels subjected to impact loading using progressive failure finite element analysis.

One form of in situ crack which has received attention is the circumferential through-crack. Barnes, Kumosa, and Hull (3) have used the finite element method in the prediction of fracture parameters at the tip of a circumferential through-crack in thin-walled filament wound glass/polyester tubes loaded in torsion. Kumosa and Hull (4), Sanders (5), and Forman, Hickman, and Shivakumar (6) provide additional information concerning the problem of a circumferential through-crack. Bucholz, Schulte-Frankenfeld, and Meiners (7) address the problem of fiber/matrix debonding in a fiber/matrix cylinder. The interface crack problem has also been reviewed by Comninou (8). The above papers notwithstanding, the delamination problem appears to remain an open issue in filament wound composite cylinders

While several researchers have investigated the effect of delamination on the structural response of composite plates and/or beams, very little exists in the literature regarding this effect on filament wound composite cylinders. In the current paper, the results from several case studies involving the effect of delaminations on the structural properties of various two-ply composite cylinders loaded in axial tension are presented. In all cases, the objective is to quantify the effect of delamination through a reduction in axial stiffness of the cylinder.

Two different crack geometries are considered. The first, referred to as a circumferential crack, is a delamination that extends the entire length of the cylinder but only through a given range of the cylindrical coordinate θ (Figure 1). In examining the effects of such a crack, we shall consider the case wherein a cylinder contains two of these cracks, located symmetrically about the x-z and y-z planes. Assuming this symmetry enables us to model only one quarter of the cylinder and to use a coarse mesh. The second crack geometry, referred to as an axial crack, is a delamination that extends through the entire range of θ but only through a given range of the cylindrical coordinate z (Figure 2). Here too, symmetry enables us to restrict our modelling to one quarter of the cylinder. In all cases, it is the first quadrant ($0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$) of the cylinder that is modelled.

Figure 1. Circumferential Crack

Figure 2. Axial Crack

2. FINITE ELEMENT CODE

In order to conduct the analysis, the authors have developed a three dimensional orthotropic linear elastostatic finite element program (ELAS3) suitable for the analysis of laminated cylinders of arbitrary stacking sequence and wall thickness. The code includes automated mesh generators which have enabled efficient parametric studies relating reduced stiffness to crack length. The element chosen for this research is an eight node isoparametric "brick" with Lagrangian shape functions. This element has three degrees of freedom per node (the three displacements). The program is written in FORTRAN and is described in detail in Zocher (9).

3. CASE STUDIES

In this section, the results from three case studies on the effects of delamination on the structural properties of various two-ply composite cylinders are presented. In each of these cases, the initial undeformed, uncracked cylinder has an inner radius of 50.55 mm, an outer radius of 50.80 mm, a length of 25.40 mm, and is composed of an orthotropic material system representative of graphite/epoxy. The mechanical properties of the material system are shown in Table 1. Each cylinder is loaded in axial tension by an evenly distributed load of 6.8947 MPa applied to one end of the cylinder with the other end constrained from displacement in the z-direction.

Table 1. Material Properties

$E_1 = 137.9 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.30$	$G_{12} = 9.65 \text{ GPa}$
$E_2 = 13.8 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{13} = 0.25$	$G_{13} = 8.27 \text{ GPa}$
$E_3 = 13.8 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{23} = 0.25$	$G_{23} = 8.27 \text{ GPa}$

Case 1 In case study one, we consider the effect of a circumferential crack in a composite cylinder having a $[0/90]$ layup. After conducting the analysis of an uncracked cylinder to establish a baseline stiffness, several cylinders with cracks of varying lengths were analyzed to predict stiffness loss versus crack length. The cracks investigated in case one were all $n(3.98 \text{ mm})$ in length, with n taking on integer values from one to twenty inclusive. These crack length increments correspond to increments of 4.5° as measured in the θ direction.

As has been previously stated; by taking symmetry into account, we have been able to solve the boundary value problems by modelling only one fourth of the cylinder. As a representation for the twenty-one runs made in the case one study, the finite element discretization for a cylinder with a 47.76 mm (54°) circumferential crack is shown in Figure 3. In the finite element model, the nodes along the plane $z = 0$ are constrained from displacement in the z -direction, the nodes along the plane $x = 0$ are constrained in the x -direction, and the nodes along the plane $y = 0$ are constrained in the y -direction. All case one models have a forty element discretization, as represented by Figure 3. The 40 element discretization was chosen for the study based on the results of a convergence study. The cracks are modelled as having zero stiffness. It should be noted that ply thicknesses and the crack thickness have been exaggerated in Figure 3 for clarity. The crack thickness modelled was taken to be $2.54 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}$ (2% of the ply thickness) between all element boundaries excluding those located at the crack tip where the crack thickness was modelled to taper from $2.54 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}$ to zero.

Figure 3. Representative Discretization for Circumferential Crack Problem

The results for the case one study are presented in Figures 4 and 5. In Figure 4, normalized stiffness has been plotted against normalized crack length. By normalized crack length, we mean this: an abscissa of 0.1 corresponds to a 7.96 mm (9°) circumferential crack (which extends through 10% of the interply bondline in the quarter cylinder modelled), an abscissa of 0.2 corresponds to a 15.92 mm (18°) crack (which extends 20% of the interply bondline), and so on. A normalized crack length of 1.0 corresponds to essentially total delamination, with the bondline intact only along one line in the model which runs the length of the cylinder at $\theta = 90^\circ$. We see (Figure 4) that a circumferential crack extending through about 14% of the interply bondline produces a 10% reduction in stiffness, and that as the crack grows, the stiffness decreases accordingly to approach a lower bound for total delamination. Note that the prediction from ELAS3 for total delamination is slightly above the theoretical value (which is 0.33). The error here (9%) is not in the code however, but in the fact that a normalized crack length of 1.0 does not truly represent total delamination since there is still one line of contact between the two plies for a 79.60 mm (90°) circumferential crack.

An equivalent alternative to quantifying the effect of damage through a reduction in stiffness is to quantify the damage through an increase in compliance. A benefit of doing this is that one may then use the relationship between compliance and crack length to extract energy release rate versus crack length as described in Broek (10). The energy release rate G is found according to Eq. 1.

$$G = \frac{dU}{dA} = \frac{1}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} P^2 \tag{1}$$

where U is the elastic energy stored in the cylinder, P is the applied load, C is the compliance, B is the crack "width", and a is the crack length.

Using the compliance method then, we have been able to derive curves of ERR versus crack length from the finite element results. Compliance and ERR curves are shown plotted against crack length in Figure 5. The slope of the compliance curve (needed in Eq. 1) was taken from a polynomial curve fit of the compliance data rather than from the data itself.

Figure 4. Stiffness vs Circumferential Crack Length, [0/90] Layup

Figure 5. Compliance and ERR vs Circumferential Crack Length, [0/90] Layup

Case 2 In case study two, we consider the effect that a circumferential crack has on axial stiffness for cylinders with several different layups. The layups considered are all of the form $[+\alpha/-\alpha]$ where α takes on multiples of five, ranging from five to sixty-five. These cylinders were modelled exactly as those of case one.

The results for case two are presented in Figures 6-12. Figures 6 and 7 present normalized stiffness versus normalized crack length for all of the layups considered. We see that, regardless of the crack length, loss in stiffness of a $[+\alpha/-\alpha]$ layup becomes more severe as α increases from zero, reaches a peak about 25° or 30° , and then becomes less severe. This is seen perhaps more clearly, by considering a plot of normalized stiffness versus α for a given crack length. We have done this in Figure 8 for a 47.76 mm (54°) circumferential crack. We would obtain similarly shaped curves for other crack lengths. Representative plots of compliance and ERR versus crack length for four of the $[+\alpha/-\alpha]$ layups considered are shown in Figures 9-12.

Figure 6. Stiffness vs Circumferential Crack Length, Layups $[+05/-05]$ Through $[+30/-30]$

Figure 7. Stiffness vs Circumferential Crack Length, Layups $[+30/-30]$ Through $[+65/-65]$

Figure 8. Stiffness vs Layup, 47.76 mm (54°) Circumferential Crack

Figure 9. Compliance and ERR vs Circumferential Crack Length [+15/-15] Layup

Figure 10. Compliance and ERR vs Circumferential Crack Length [+30/-30] Layup

Figure 11. Compliance and ERR vs Circumferential Crack Length [+45/-45] Layup

Figure 12. Compliance and ERR vs Circumferential Crack Length [+60/-60] Layup

Case 3 In case study three, we consider the effect of an axial crack in a composite cylinder having a [0/90] layup. After conducting the analysis of an uncracked cylinder to establish a baseline stiffness, five additional BVP's were solved to predict loss in stiffness for a given crack length. The crack lengths investigated range from 5.08 mm to 25.40 mm (total delamination) with the crack length increasing incrementally by 5.08 mm in each successive run. As a representative for the runs made in the course of conducting the case three study, the finite element discretization for the cylinder with a 15.24 mm axial crack is shown in Figure 13. Ply and crack thicknesses have been exaggerated in Figure 13 for clarity.

Figure 13. Representative Discretization for Axial Crack Problem

The results for case three are presented in Figures 14 and 15. In Figure 14, we have plotted normalized axial stiffness against normalized crack length. By normalized crack length, we mean this: an abscissa of 0.1 corresponds to an axial crack extending 10% of the length of the cylinder, an abscissa of 0.2 corresponds to 20%, and so on. Obviously, a normalized crack length of 1.0 represents total delamination. We see (Figure 14) that an axial crack extending about 7.5% of the length of the cylinder produces a 10% reduction in stiffness, and that as the crack grows, the stiffness decreases accordingly to approach a lower limit for total delamination. Note that the normalized stiffness corresponding to total delamination is roughly the same in Figures 4 and 14. This is as it should be since the layups of these two cases are the same and the end result of total delamination, whether by growth of a circumferential crack or an axial crack, is the same. In Figure 15 we have plotted compliance and ERR against crack length.

Figure 14. Stiffness vs Axial Crack Length [0/90] Layup

Figure 15. Compliance and ERR vs Axial Crack Length, [0/90] Layup

5. CONCLUSIONS

Three dimensional finite element analyses have been used in a study on the effects of delamination in filament wound composite cylinders loaded in tension. In these analyses, the effect of this damage has been quantified through a reduction in axial stiffness for the cylinder. It has been shown that, under the boundary conditions imposed in the case studies presented herein, the reduction in stiffness can be substantial. Compliance and ERR, as well as axial stiffness have been presented as functions of crack length. Two crack geometries (circumferential and axial) and several different layups have been considered.

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8. BIOGRAPHIES

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